

MOBILE APP-BASED TEACHING, RESEARCH, AND SUPERVISION MANAGEMENT PLATFORM FOR FACULTY MEMBERS

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ABSTRACT

The pervasive growth of digital and mobile technologies has transformed various aspects of our daily lives. Particularly noteworthy is the integration of these technologies into the field of education, sparking a revolution in traditional teaching methods and ushering in innovative solutions for educational practitioners. Mobile learning, hailed as the future of education has given rise to platforms that serve as centralized hubs for lecturers, facilitating the convenient planning and management of their academic activities. By leveraging such platforms, education practitioners can efficiently streamline their workflows and enrich student communication channels. The flexibility afforded by these platforms represents a paradigm shift in how lecturers can navigate their professional responsibilities, bringing about a new era of accessibility and efficiency in academic pursuits. The app is developed using the Flutter platform. The mobile app effectively bridges the gap between physical and virtual classrooms through its intuitive interface and comprehensive array of learning resources. This app stands as evidence of the possibilities and advantages of innovative eLearning solutions.

Keywords: Mobile learning, Education, Digital environment, Technology

INTRODUCTION

THE increasing availability of technology-enabled learning tools in education has led scholars to explore ways to enhance learning using emerging technologies such as mobile apps. The name “app” denotes application software. A mobile app is software for mobile devices, such as laptops, tablets, smartphones, iPads, and iPods (Hinze *et al.*, 2022). The concept of online learning has gained significant traction in recent years, with platforms like UdeMy revolutionizing how people acquire knowledge and skills. An online learning platform offers a digital environment where learners can access various courses across various subjects taught by instructors worldwide. These platforms provide flexibility, convenience, and personalized learning experiences. The rapid advancement of technology has transformed the traditional education landscape, making online learning an integral part of modern educational systems (Braun *et al.*, 2021). Several Mobile app-based teaching, research, and supervision management platforms exist for lecturers, such as Blackboard Mobile, Canvas Teachers, Moodle Mobile, Edmodo, and Schoology. Each platform provides a distinct collection of features and functionalities to meet the different demands of educators, equipping them with the tools they require to manage their professional duties efficiently (Chen *et al.*, 2024; Crompton and Burke, 2018). The use of technology in education is becoming increasingly prevalent in today's educational atmosphere. Mobile learning through technology, while balancing its benefits and difficulties, is positioned to play

an ever-expanding role in influencing the educational experiences of today's undergraduates.

A Learning Management System (LMS) is a software designed to deliver, monitor, and administer training or educational programs (Smith and Lynch, 2010). These systems vary, encompassing tools for managing educational records, distributing courses online, and facilitating collaborative activities (Lynch, 2012). The development and upkeep of comprehensive learning content necessitate significant initial and ongoing human effort.

The widespread use of e-learning, and LMS specifically is not without its difficulties. While technology facilitates new forms of communication and cooperation, it also brings potential distractions. Individuals may become distracted from their learning objectives due to the ease with which they may engage in social activities, such as communication on social platforms. Furthermore, the ease of access to internet resources raises concerns about academic integrity, since students may resort to cheating during online examinations and quizzes by using search engines. In addition, lecturers frequently have demanding schedules and require the flexibility to handle their teaching, research, and supervision duties while moving.

A mobile app-based platform enables quick access to critical tools and resources, allowing employees to stay connected and productive from any location at any time. The developed app aims to enhance the productivity, communication, collaboration, and professional growth of lecturers by providing a centralized and user-friendly

solution that empowers lecturers to excel in their roles and deliver high-quality education. A mobile app-based platform gives quick access to critical tools and resources, allowing users to stay connected and productive from any location at any time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The landscape of education has been significantly transformed by the advent of technology, particularly with the emergence of various educational technology (EdTech) companies and platforms (Naismith *et al.*, 2004). In recent years, these platforms have played a pivotal role in enhancing learning experiences, both inside and outside traditional classroom settings. This literature review aims to explore and analyze some prominent players in the field of educational technology, focusing specifically on learning management systems (LMS) and online learning platforms (Masters, 2024).

Within the educational technology ecosystem, several key players have emerged, each offering unique solutions to meet the diverse needs of students, educators, and institutions. Notable among these are Blackboard Inc., Canvas Teachers by Instructure Inc., Moodle Pty Ltd, Schoology, Udacity, Khan Academy, Coursera, Teachable, YouTube, and ResearchGate. These platforms vary in their functionalities, target audiences, and pedagogical approaches, yet they collectively contribute to the broader landscape of digital education (Temple, 2009; Chafkin, 2024; Yu *et al.*, 2016; Allgaier, 2019).

A significant trend within this ecosystem is the proliferation of mobile learning applications, catering to the increasingly mobile lifestyles of both students and educators. Platforms such as Blackboard Mobile, Canvas Teachers, Moodle Mobile, and Khan Academy leverage the ubiquity of smartphones to provide on-the-go access to course materials, interactive content, and communication tools (Dreifus, 2024). This emphasis on mobile accessibility reflects a shift towards flexible, personalized learning experiences that transcend traditional classroom boundaries.

Beyond content delivery, many of these platforms facilitate collaboration and networking among learners, educators, and researchers. Learning management systems like Schoology and Canvas Teachers enable seamless communication and collaboration within virtual learning environments, while ResearchGate serves as a professional network for scientists and researchers to share papers, exchange ideas, and find collaborators (Yu *et al.*, 2016). These collaborative features enhance engagement, foster knowledge sharing, and extend learning beyond the confines of traditional classrooms.

METHODOLOGY

Mobile Learning is a term to denote learning involving a mobile device. The term is fully defined as “learning across multiple contexts, through social and content interactions,

using personal electronic devices” (Crompton and Burke, 2018). Lecturers frequently have demanding schedules and require the flexibility to handle their teaching, research, and supervision duties while on the move. Figures 1 and 2 present the entity relationship and flow diagrams. The major user is the Lecturer or Faculty Member and there are three major aspects to be managed: teaching, research, and supervision which are the fundamental responsibilities of a Faculty Member.

Figure 1: Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 2: Entity Relationship Diagram

To address security concerns and ensure only authorized users can access the platform, a multi-factor authentication using a combination of password protection and a one-time password is implemented. Users, including lecturers and students, are assigned role-based access privileges. This restricts access to sensitive information based on their role. This is important because it ensures only legitimate users

can access specific areas of the platform, reducing the risk of unauthorized access. All sensitive data, including research files, student records, and supervision logs is encrypted both in transit (data over network) and at rest (all stored data) by implementing the Transport Layer Security (TLS) for encrypting data transmitted between the app and the server.

To prevent injection attacks, thorough input validation is implemented across all forms and APIs used in the application. This ensures that any data entered by users is sanitized and validated before processing. Additionally, API rate limiting is ensured to prevent brute-force attacks on login and other sensitive endpoints. The platform categorizes data into temporary and permanent types to ensure appropriate storage and security management. Each data type is treated differently based on its purpose and lifecycle. Temporary data refers to information that is required only for short periods and is automatically discarded when no longer needed. Examples include cache content, and session data. Permanent data consists of critical information that needs to be stored over a long time. Example includes user profile, and research data.

Several key stakeholders are incentivized to protect the data generated by the platform each has different motivations for ensuring data protection, ranging from legal compliance to maintaining institutional integrity and user trust. Faculty members responsible for managing research and supervising students have a strong incentive to protect the data they handle. A breach in data security could undermine their academic standing. Institutional administrators and IT staff are incentivized by the need to comply with data protection laws, maintain the institution's reputation, and avoid breaches that could result in financial penalties or loss of trust.

Plate 1: Courses and Video Playing Page

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The splash screen is a visual element that briefly appears during the launch of an application, providing users with feedback that the application is in the process of loading. The design for the MARTS app is thoughtfully crafted to convey brand identity and contribute positively to the overall user experience. The login and sign-in page is a critical component of any application, providing users with secure access to their accounts and personalizing their experience. The homepage of the mobile learning app is intricately designed to serve as the central gateway for users embarking on their digital learning journey. Its design prioritizes aesthetics and strategically organizes elements to ensure an intuitive and engaging user experience. Fundamental to its design are clear and easily navigable menus, guiding users seamlessly through various sections and functionalities. Plates 1 and 2 present some of the major screens.

Plate 2: Publication Page

The courses and video-playing pages in an e-learning app are critical components that directly impact the learning experience. A publication page typically serves as a centralized space within the mobile application where various types of content, such as articles, research papers, blog posts, or other written materials, are presented and organized.

CONCLUSION

The research is centered on meeting the contemporary demand for accessible and interactive learning tools, a focus that permeates its design and implementation. A notable strength of the app lies in its intuitive user interfaces, fostering a seamless and engaging learning experience. The incorporation of responsive design ensures accessibility

across diverse devices, catering to the varied needs of learners. Features like real-time collaboration, progress tracking, and personalized learning paths add sophistication to the eLearning experience, not only improving platform usability but also significantly enhancing the effectiveness of the learning process. Moreover, the emphasis on robust security measures reflects a keen awareness of privacy concerns, prioritizing the confidentiality of user data.

While the current iteration of the app showcases commendable achievements, there exists potential for further improvement and expansion. Future iterations could explore the integration of adaptive learning algorithms to customize content based on individual progress and learning styles. Introducing gamification elements could inject an element of fun and motivation into the learning journey, potentially boosting user engagement.

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